

Leveraging Active Learning for Ocean Data Quality Assessment: Reducing Labeling Workload and Addressing Severe Data Imbalance Challenges

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Abstract

Oceanic research initiatives like Argo, GLOSS, and EMSO aim to enhance our understanding of the oceans and climate through extensive data collection. Maintaining the quality of collected data is essential for effective data analysis and real-world applications. While automated and semi-automated tests can provide real-time or near-real-time validation, thorough quality control still depends on operator review. Consequently, current Quality Control (QC) processes continue to be labor-intensive. Machine Learning (ML) methods, which can analyze vast amounts of data and learn complex patterns autonomously, offer significant potential for improving QC processes. However, challenges like severe data disproportion persist for ML approaches. This article proposes exploiting Active Learning (AL) to assist QC experts, reducing their workload by proactively selecting informative data points for labeling. Targeting the data distribution challenge, AL, coupled with imbalance-resilient classifiers, enhances model performance in recognizing erroneous data points. To mitigate the cold-start problem in AL, we propose outlier detection for initializing classifiers, significantly reducing annotation costs. Our approach is tested on data generated by 5 Argo floats, demonstrating its feasibility to lessen the labeling workload for experts and tackle significant data imbalance. Although the experiments are limited in scale, the findings indicate a promising outlook for using active learning in ocean data quality assessment, facilitating an effective semi-automated quality control framework.

Keywords: Ocean data quality control, Initial set construction, Data Imbalance, Active learning

1 Introduction

Numerous global initiatives such as Array for Real-time Geostrophic Oceanography (Argo) [1], Global Sea Level Observing System (GLOSS) [2],

and European Multidisciplinary Seafloor Observatory (EMSO) [3], have been established to gather oceanic data at various depths, aimed at advancing ocean and climate research. Argo, for instance, operates a vast network of profiling

instruments across the world’s oceans, generating extensive observational datasets over time. Nonetheless, these datasets often encounter quality issues stemming from sensor drift, transient dirt, and transmission errors, which can potentially compromise the accuracy of scientific analyses. Thus, it is crucial to ensure data quality through rigorous Quality Control (QC) procedures before its utilization in subsequent analyses. Given the stringent standards for data credibility, QC procedures typically rely on domain experts or require substantial human involvement, making them labor-intensive and time-consuming.

This critical issue is attracting more and more research attention. Various automated data quality assessment approaches have been proposed to assist QC operators. Traditional methods apply a sequence of rule-based statistical tests on the data instances [4–6]. These methods rely on pre-defined quality criteria and are subject to specific observation types. As a result, it can only perform basic examination for the validity of data and still depends on manual inspection for accurate outputs. In contrast, an emerging research direction is to exploit Machine Learning (ML) methods for ocean data quality assessment [7–9]. One branch of studies utilizes anomaly detection techniques to identify erroneous measurements from the dataset [7, 9]. Another line of research employs deep neural networks to classify samples into different quality categories [8].

Fully automated methods remain in the early stages for conducting expert-level quality assessments, largely due to the dynamic characteristics of ocean observation data and the complexity of error patterns. Consequently, our goal is to develop a semi-automated framework that supports human experts, helping to reduce their workload while ensuring reliable quality assessments. We identify two main challenges remaining in the QC research. The first challenge is the significant reliance on human involvement. As the volume of ocean data continuously increases, manually labeling data points has introduced a substantial workload to human experts, which is not only inefficient but also error-prone. The second obstacle involves severe data imbalance concerning the quality labels. The erroneous measurements typically constitute less than 1% of the dataset, which can degrade classifier performance for minority classes, leading to lower effectiveness

in identifying incorrect observations within the dataset [10].

To address the challenge of extensive human involvement, we propose leveraging Active Learning (AL) techniques [11] to minimize the number of labeled instances needed for training ML models. AL approaches can pinpoint the most informative data points for labeling to update models, thereby enhancing model performance even with a limited number of labeled examples. Within the domain of data quality assessment, AL can identify the most challenging samples requiring manual inspection and automate quality assessment for the remainder of the dataset. Consequently, this approach significantly reduces the workload for human analysts while maintaining high model performance.

Additionally, our thorough analysis indicates that AL can also indirectly tackle the issue of distribution skewness by selecting a high proportion of erroneous samples, facilitating highly efficient classifier learning with only a small subset of labeled samples. Nonetheless, data imbalance introduces another challenge, i.e., *cold-start problem* to AL methods. To bootstrap an AL process, a small set of labeled data called the initial set is usually required to initialize the classifiers [11]. If not initialized properly, classifiers will yield ineffective selections of samples for labeling and fail the AL approach. However, a small initial set built from a severely distorted dataset likely contains zero erroneous instances for training meaningful classifiers, which consequentially misleads the AL query process. This is referred to as the *cold-start problem*. To address this issue, we exploit outlier detectors for initial set construction, which can increase the possibility of incorporating erroneous samples in initial sets and improve the effectiveness of classifier initialization.

In this article, we present an AL-based QC-assistance framework for ocean data quality assessment, aiming to reduce the workload of QC experts in a semi-automated workflow. The feasibility of our method is tested on data from 5 Argo floats [12]. This manuscript builds upon our preliminary findings presented in BigData [13]. Here, we extend the work by providing a more comprehensive analysis, including additional experiments and in-depth discussions on the data imbalance challenge. Our contributions are summarized below:

- We present a novel AL-based data quality assessment framework to reduce the workload of human analysts;
- We tackle the data imbalance problem with resilient classifiers;
- We demonstrate the effectiveness of AL in addressing the data imbalance problem under a restricted number of labeled samples;
- We propose utilizing outlier detection for initial set construction to solve the cold-start problem and minimize the overall annotation cost.

2 Related work

2.1 General QC Methods for Ocean Data

Automated QC approaches on large-scale ocean observatory data have been studied to support human experts. Classical automated QC procedures involve constant value check, spike and step check, range check, and stability check [5, 6, 14] in order to screen out gross errors from measurements. However, these approaches are subject to human experts for fine-grained quality examination. More advanced methods utilize ML models, such as Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) and ARIMA, to analyze large-scale data [7–9]. Another widely adopted approach for quality assessment is anomaly detection, considering the infrequent occurrence of erroneous samples. Castelão [9] characterizes the typical behavior of the data by estimating a probability density function (PDF) for each feature, and the survival function (SF) of the estimated PDF is used to quantify the anomalousness of a certain measurement. This approach reduces the error by at least 50% when applied to 13 years of hydrographic profiles. Zhou et al. [7] focus on time-series data and employ the ARIMA model to detect erroneous measurements. The proposed method was applied to pH and CTD data from the Xiaoqushan Seafloor Observatory and achieved an F1 score of 0.9506 in outlier detection (the definition of F1 score can be found in Section 6.3). However, ARIMA is a time series forecasting model that requires clean and well-preprocessed time series data for training, which implicitly demands quality labels for historical data points.

Different from the above methods, Mieruch et al. [8] frame data quality assessment as a

binary classification problem, where each sample is categorized as of *good* or *bad* qualities. They present SalaciaML, aiming to mimic the skillful QC experts with a deep neural network in identifying potentially erroneous samples. A MLP is trained on more than 2 million temperature measurements over the Mediterranean Seas spanning the last 100 years and detects correctly more than 90% of all good and/or bad data in 11 out of 16 Mediterranean regions.

The high accuracy achieved by the aforementioned studies is at the cost of a large amount of labeled data, which is usually difficult and expensive to obtain and presents significant challenges in real-world applications.

2.2 Argo QC Tests

As Argo data is utilized in our experiments, we outline the specific tests applied within the Argo data QC process [4], including four main steps:

Real-time quality control automatic tests. These profile-level tests achieve high True Positive rates with minimal False Positives.

Real-time or near-real-time quality control semi-automatic test. These tests provide higher True Positive rates but with more False Positives. Due to their False Positive amount, they cannot flag automatically. Instead, these tests generate warnings that require an operator’s review. Currently, two semi-automatic tests are used: the optimal analyses tool¹ [15] and the MinMax test [16].

Delayed mode quality control. This stage uses reference datasets and a specified methodology (the OWC method) to calibrate for potential sensor biases and slopes. It involves a comprehensive review at the float level across the entire time series, with operators utilizing any suitable visualization tools.

Basin-wide consistency check. This step ensures consistency across a basin and is conducted by the Argo Regional Centers (ARCs).

2.3 Data Balancing Solutions

Data imbalance can significantly impact classifiers’ performance [17]. Numerous methods have been developed to address this challenge, which generally fall into three categories: data-level

¹<https://www.seanoe.org/data/00412/52367/>

methods that focus on modifying the data, algorithm-level methods that adjust the algorithms, or a combination of both in hybrid approaches [18]. Data-level methods aim to rebalance the class distribution through the manipulation of the data itself, mainly involving techniques like oversampling the minority class, e.g., Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) [19], undersampling the majority class [20], and a combination of both oversampling and undersampling strategies [21]. Algorithm-level methods keep the data unchanged but modify existing learning algorithms to make them more robust to imbalance. Commonly utilized approaches include cost-sensitive learning [22] that penalizes misclassifications of the minority class more than those of the majority class by adjusting models’ loss functions, and ensemble techniques such as boosting (e.g., AdaBoost [23] and Gradient Boosting Machines (GBMs)[24, 25]) and bagging (e.g., Random Forest (RF) [26]) that exploit a set of models to improve the classification of minority class samples.

In addressing the data distribution challenge in ocean data quality assessment tasks, we prefer algorithm-level methods to data-level methods since it is crucial to maintain the integrity of data in a QC scenario. Besides, algorithm-level methods offer other advantages, including greater flexibility and control over the learning process, generalizability across different datasets, and computational efficiency.

2.4 Labeling Cost Reduction with Active Learning

Active Learning (AL) is a subset of ML methods designed to reduce the labeling effort required to train a model while maintaining or even improving its performance [11]. It has been widely used across various domains [27–29]. AL is primarily an iterative learning process, where a learning model is initially trained on a small set of labeled data and continually updated with newly labeled instances. An oracle is included in this process, providing ground truth labels to the learning model. AL employs a query strategy to select instances that are expected to yield the greatest improvement in model performance for labeling, whether through uncertainty sampling, diversity sampling, or other methods [11]. There are two

main AL scenarios, i.e., pool-based, where all unlabeled instances are available upfront, and stream-based, where data arrives sequentially.

In this work, we apply pool-based AL methods to the ocean data quality assessment challenge to reduce QC experts’ workload. An unlabeled dataset is given for quality assessment; A human expert will play the oracle who labels any queried samples. The learning models are classifiers that predict quality labels for input data instances. They can select instances from the dataset through query strategies and request labeling from human experts. As quality labels are provided by QC experts, reducing the number of labeled samples is considered equivalent to reducing experts’ workload.

3 Data Analysis

3.1 Data Source

We use ocean observatory data provided by Argo [1], an international program that collects subsurface ocean water properties such as temperature, salinity, and oxygen across the global earth using a fleet of robotic instruments. The instruments called *floats* or *profilers* drift with the ocean currents and move up and down between the surface and a mid-water level. The first float came into service in 1996. Each year, new floats are deployed into the ocean to replace the retired floats and increase the coverage of the observing network. As of 28th August 2023, there have been 18,304 floats being deployed across the globe, with 3,646 being active and 14,658 inactive.

As illustrated in Figure 1, a typical Argo float movement cycle begins with an initial floating depth of approximately 1 kilometer below sea level. After drifting at this depth for about 9 days, the float descends to 2 kilometers before ascending to the ocean surface. As the float rises, it measures water properties, including temperature and salinity, through the water column. Upon reaching the surface, the float transmits these data and its geographic location to data facilities via satellite.

The data is gathered, decoded, and subjected to real-time quality control (RTQC) tests at Data Assembly Centres (DACs). There are 11 DACs in total. After being flagged, the data from the DACs is sent to Global Data Assembly Centers (GDACs), of which there are two:

Fig. 1: A typical Argo float movement cycle. Source from Argo. <https://argo.ucsd.edu/how-do-floats-work/>

one located at Ifremer in France and the other at US GODAE. These two GDACs provide redundancy, and they synchronize their data repositories daily. The regional centers are responsible for ensuring the quality of Argo data, detecting potential outliers, and providing feedback to data centers. These data were collected and made freely available by the International Argo Program and the national programs that contribute to it [12]. (<https://argo.ucsd.edu>, [://www.oceanops.org](http://www.oceanops.org)). The Argo Program is part of the Global Ocean Observing System.

We utilize the Euro Argo data selection tool² to select floats and download data with “Delayed-mode” quality flags, as they have been fully reviewed by human experts. Figure 2 illustrates an example of the temperature profiles and the salinity profiles produced by the float numbered “4903220” spanning from March 2019 to August 2023.

3.2 Data Characteristics

Oceanographic data exhibits strong temporal and spatial dependencies [8]. It is usually assumed that data collected from the same geographic area at the same time are consistent. Considering that the measurements depend on temporal and spatial factors, we introduce time and location (including longitude and latitude) dimensions as additional features to implicitly model these relationships.

The ocean observatory data is also characterized by its unpredictable nature and often exceedingly low error rates. Extremely low error

ratios, such as those below 1%, lead to severe class imbalance that may compromise classifier performances. In such scenarios, some studies employ anomaly detection algorithms to identify erroneous samples, treating data instances with quality issues as anomalies. These approaches often assume that erroneous observations significantly deviate from normal ones. However, quality assessment presents a complex challenge, as many erroneous samples may still fall within the normal data distribution. Furthermore, anomaly detection methods typically assume that erroneous data is rare. However, given the high variability in error ratios, such methods may not be suitable for datasets with error rates around 30%. Thus, it is more appropriate to frame the quality assessment task as a classification problem rather than an anomaly detection problem.

4 Problem Definition

This section presents the formal definition of the ocean data quality assessment problem. Let $x_c^p \in \mathbb{R}$ be a measurement for a parameter p given a position and time coordinate $c = (x, y, z, t)$. An observation containing a set of parameters is then represented as $[x_c^{p_1}, x_c^{p_2}, \dots, x_c^{p_d}]$. For simplicity, we will denote it as x_c thereafter. Each observation x_c is associated with a quality label y_c . In this work, we only consider binary quality labels, where each instance is either *with* OR *without quality issues*, and thus we have $y_c \in \{0, 1\}$. The quality flag 1 means *there are quality issues* in the data instance (also called *erroneous sample*), while the quality flag 0 means there is no quality problem. The task of quality assessment is to classify whether a data instance has quality issues, i.e., to assign a quality flag $\hat{y}_c \in \{0, 1\}$ to observation x_c .

Under the circumstances considered by this work, the quality labels $\{y_c\}$ are unknown at the beginning. However, QC experts can reveal the ground truth label y_c^* for any sample x_c^* selected from the dataset D . The goal of this work is to maximize the quality assessment model’s prediction ability while minimizing the number of selected samples. Additionally, the dataset D suffers from severe data imbalance regarding their quality labels where the number of samples with label 1 is much smaller than those with label 0, i.e., $N(y_c = 1) \ll N(y_c = 0)$. Typically, the proportion of erroneous data is less than 1%.

²<https://dataselection.euro-argo.eu/>

Fig. 2: Visualization of Argo profiling data. The blank area denotes QC4 (bad data) for salinity and missing data for temperature. The missing data for temperature were not flagged (QC=' '). Float code: 4903220.

5 AL-based QC-assistance Framework

The AL approach is especially well-suited for supporting analysts in data quality assessment tasks. It allows assessment models to interact directly with human experts, soliciting labels to improve their performance. Due to AL’s high data efficiency, human experts can label far fewer samples than required by traditional supervised training methods to build an effective QC system. Thus, we propose an AL-based QC assistance framework for large-scale ocean observatory data. This section provides an overview of the framework’s primary structure and key components.

5.1 Framework Structure

Figure 3 illustrates the structure of the proposed framework, which is human-in-the-loop that places human experts at the core of significant decision-making processes while leveraging AL to streamline their workload. The framework comprises two main phases: *Initial set construction* and *Active learning cycles*. In the initial set construction phase, we establish an initial set D_I using outlier/anomaly detectors in order to incorporate erroneous data samples in the initial set due to the typical low erroneous rate. These detectors identify the top- N_I outlier samples from the target dataset D , with N_I denoting the size of D_I . The remaining samples constitute the unlabeled set D_U . The samples in D_I are then labeled by human experts and used to initialize the classifier.

During the AL cycles, the target models act as quality assessors that assign quality labels to data instances. Human experts serve as the oracle that provides legitimate quality labels for queried samples chosen based on a *query strategy*. The accumulating labeled samples are denoted as the labeled set D_L . The AL workflow includes the following steps:

1. The classifiers are initialized using the initial set (Step ①).
2. The classifiers produce intermediate results for the query strategy to select the K most informative samples (Step ②).
3. The selected instances are presented to human experts for labeling. Meanwhile, they are moved from the unlabeled set to the labeled set (Step ③).
4. The classification models are updated using the labeled set (Step ④).
5. Repeat Steps ②, ③, and ④ until the annotation budget (if given) exhausts or the performance threshold is reached.

As depicted in Figure 3, the class distribution w.r.t. quality flags tends to be significantly uneven, with only a small fraction representing erroneous samples. Hence, employing classifiers that are resilient to imbalance becomes crucial for effective quality assessment. Furthermore, it’s essential to include erroneous samples in the initial set to ensure that the classification models are properly initialized for subsequent AL cycles. However, this task becomes challenging when the

Fig. 3: Structure of the proposed AL-based ocean data QC framework

size of the initial set is strictly limited, thus motivating the use of outlier detectors for constructing the initial set. It is worth noting that although anomaly detection methods are not suitable for the ocean data quality assessment task due to the variation of erroneous data ratios, applying anomaly detection methods only in the initial set construction procedure improves the possibility of incorporating erroneous samples in the initial set in any erroneous data ratios and thus keeps the flexibility of the proposed framework.

5.2 AL Query Strategies

A *query strategy* in AL refers to the policy or criterion utilized for selecting data samples from an unlabeled dataset for labeling [11]. The efficacy of an AL method heavily hinges on its query strategy, as it determines which samples are chosen for model training. Moreover, it is important to recognize the interdependence between query strategies and target models. The query strategy relies on the outputs from classifiers to rank instances, and in turn, the classifiers are further trained by using the samples selected by the query strategy. This mutual reliance ensures that both components work collaboratively to effectively guide the labeling process in AL. We investigate various query strategies for selecting samples from the unlabeled

dataset. Initially, we employ the Uncertainty-based Sampling (US) method for individual classifiers. Subsequently, we delve into ensemble query strategies that necessitate the involvement of more than one classifier in decision-making.

5.2.1 Uncertainty-based Sampling

The Uncertainty-based Sampling (US) method is based on the assumption that the more uncertain one classifier is about its predictions, the more informative the input samples are deemed to be. Thus, it will be more useful for optimizing the classifier. We employ the entropy of predicted probabilities as the uncertainty measure to implement the US method [11]. Supposing that given a sample x_c , a classifier ϕ can output the class probabilities $P_\phi(\hat{y}_c|x_c)$, $\hat{y}_c \in \{0, 1\}$, then the entropy-based uncertainty of this classifier over sample x_c is defined as:

$$H_{EN}(x_c) = - \sum_{\hat{y}_c \in \{0,1\}} P_\phi(\hat{y}_c|x_c) \log P_\phi(\hat{y}_c|x_c). \quad (1)$$

According to the US approach, the samples with maximum uncertainty values will be chosen for labeling, which is:

$$x_{EN}^* = \arg \max_c H_{EN}(x_c). \quad (2)$$

5.2.2 Query-by-Committee Sampling

We implement the ensemble query strategy under the Query-By-Committee (QBC) [30] scenario. In contrast to US, the QBC method selects data samples through a committee consisting of several classifiers where different hypotheses are considered when computing the informativeness of the samples. We employ the Consensus-Entropy-based Sampling (CES) method for instance selection. Specifically, for a data instance x_c , each classifier ϕ_k within the committee \mathcal{M} independently predicts label probabilities $P_{\phi_k}(\hat{y}_c|x_c)$. The consensus probabilities of the committee are given by:

$$P_{\mathcal{M}}(\hat{y}_c|x_c) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{M}|} \sum_{\phi_k \in \mathcal{M}} P_{\phi_k}(\hat{y}_c|x_c), \quad (3)$$

where $|\mathcal{M}|$ denotes the committee size. The disagreement degree among the committee members is calculated as the entropy of the consensus probabilities:

$$H_{CES}(x_c) = - \sum_{\hat{y}_c \in \{0,1\}} P_{\mathcal{M}}(\hat{y}_c|x_c) \log P_{\mathcal{M}}(\hat{y}_c|x_c). \quad (4)$$

The committee then selects samples that maximize the disagreement score:

$$x_{CES}^* = \arg \max_c H_{CES}(x_c). \quad (5)$$

5.3 Initial Set Construction

Previous studies often overlook the significance of the initial set [31]. Many of them construct an initial set by randomly selecting a predetermined number of samples and excluding the labeling of this set from the annotation cost. However, this approach presents two problems. Firstly, in practical scenarios, labels for the initial set are also provided by human experts, which should be included in the overall labeling expense. Secondly, the composition of the initial set can substantially influence the subsequent AL process. Insufficient initial instances, particularly for highly disproportionate datasets, may lead to cold-start issues, while redundant initial instances can result in unnecessary annotation costs. Additionally, certain classifiers, such as Categorical Boosting (CatBoost), require a diverse range of

data classes, necessitating a large initial set when abnormal samples are scarce in the dataset, as seen in highly uneven datasets.

To address these challenges, we utilize outlier detectors (or anomaly detectors) to construct the initial set D_I . Outlier detectors can estimate the likelihood that samples are erroneous with minimal or no labeled information. By selecting a group of observations with the highest likelihood of error, as ranked by the outlier detectors, this set should, in theory, contain a higher proportion of erroneous observations than a randomly chosen set. This approach allows us to create an initial set with a more balanced mix of erroneous and error-free observations. It is particularly useful because errors are generally rare in ocean observatory data; a random selection would likely produce an extremely uneven initial set (sometimes no erroneous observations at all), leading to cold-start issues for classifiers.

One may argue that we could use outlier detectors to detect quality issues within the AL cycles. However, outlier detectors can not be applied to datasets with very high error rates, as they assume the rareness of abnormal observations. Additionally, they often underperform supervised models on classification tasks. Therefore, in this work, we utilize outlier detectors solely for constructing the initial set and implement the learning models of AL as supervised classifiers instead.

Formally, let ψ be an outlier detector that produces an outlier score $\mu_c = \psi(x_c)$ for data sample x_c . D_I is composed of the top- N_I samples from the dataset D ranked by outlier scores, i.e.,

$$D_I = \{x_c \mid \mu_c \in \text{top-}N_I \text{ outlier scores}\}, \quad (6)$$

where N_I is the size of D_I . In this work, we consider three common outlier detection algorithms, i.e., Isolation Forest (iForest) [32], One-Class Support Vector Machine (OCSVM) [33], and Local Outlier Factor (LOF) [34] and compare their performances in Section 7.5.2

6 Combating Severe Class Imbalance in Ocean Data

Ocean observatory data often includes datasets where errors are extremely rare due to the reliable performance of sensors in most conditions.

However, this creates major challenges for training and evaluating classification methods. First, it hampers the classifiers’ ability to detect erroneous data effectively. Additionally, it can cause cold-start issues for AL approaches, where classifiers and query strategies underperform due to the scarcity of error samples in the initial dataset.

Choosing appropriate evaluation metrics is another critical challenge. For instance, accuracy, a commonly used metric in classification tasks, can be misleading in the presence of highly uneven data, a phenomenon known as the accuracy paradox. Accuracy is calculated as the proportion of correctly predicted samples. In a dataset where 95% of the instances belong to one class, a classifier predicting all instances as the majority class would still achieve 95% accuracy, even though it lacks true discriminative capacity. Thus, addressing the difficulties caused by uneven datasets is essential when developing quality assessment models and utilizing AL methods. And it is equally important to select suitable metrics for assessing classifier performance on such datasets.

6.1 Classifier Selection

To address the challenge of imbalanced data at the algorithmic level, we employ classifiers that are resilient to such conditions, particularly those utilizing *Gradient Boosting (GB)* methods. GB is a ML technique applicable to both regression and classification tasks. It is an ensemble learning method that strengthens the predictive model by sequentially combining the predictions of several weaker models, usually decision trees [35]. One key benefit of GB approaches is their ability to assign greater weight to misclassified samples, giving more focus to the minority class in disproportionate datasets.

The GB-based classifiers explored in our study include Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) [25], CatBoost [36], and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) [24]. XGBoost is an ensemble algorithm utilizing gradient boosting, excelling in structured data tasks, and featuring sequential model correction. CatBoost is a gradient-boosting approach tailored for categorical data, automatically handling categorical features during training. LightGBM is a high-efficiency gradient boosting framework using

histogram-based techniques for faster training, suitable for large datasets.

6.2 Active Learning for Distribution Adjustment

In situations where data is highly skewed, the scarcity of samples becomes even more problematic. Even with classifiers designed to handle such distributions, model performance can still be heavily impacted. In these cases, AL is particularly effective when dealing with limited labeled data [37]. AL strategies tend to prioritize selecting minority class samples for labeling, recognizing the difficulties they present for classification. By adding these minority samples to the training set, the model’s ability to handle uneven data distributions improves. From a data perspective, AL methods naturally adjust the distribution within the training set, creating a more balanced representation, which supports better model learning and overall performance on skewed datasets.

6.3 Evaluation Metrics

As discussed earlier, evaluation metrics should be carefully selected. In this article, we denote erroneous samples as positive (class 1, with error) and correct ones as negative (class 0, without error). We employ a wide range of metrics to assess the performance of classifiers for comprehensive insights:

- Precision, Recall, F1-score
- Cohen’s kappa (Kappa)
- Precision-Recall Curve - Area Under the Curve (PRC-AUC)

Precision (also known as Positive Predictive Value) is defined as the proportion of true positives in all positive predictions. Mathematically, it is defined as:

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}, \quad (7)$$

where TP is the number of positive predictions that are actually positive, and FP is the number of positive predictions that are actually negative. High precision suggests that when the model predicts an observation as erroneous, the prediction is likely to be correct.

Recall (also known as Sensitivity or True Positive Rate) is the proportion of true positives that have been correctly identified out of the total actual positives, defined as:

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}, \quad (8)$$

where FN is the number of negative predictions that are actually positive. The recall metric measures the model’s ability to catch all the erroneous observations in the dataset.

We rely on both precision and recall metrics because true and false positives are interconnected and can be adjusted by modifying the classifier’s predictive threshold. Lowering the threshold makes the classifier more prone to predicting positives, which increases the capture of true positives (enhancing recall) but may also raise the count of false positives (reducing precision). On the other hand, raising the threshold results in a stricter classifier, reducing false positives (improving precision) but potentially omitting some true positives, which decreases recall.

F1-score is a summative metric built upon recall and precision. It reflects the overall performance of a classifier in reducing false positives and false negatives by balancing the trade-off between these two types of errors. It can be computed as below:

$$F1 = 2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (9)$$

An optimal F1 score suggests that the model correctly identifies erroneous data points (high precision) while also capturing the majority of these errors across the dataset (high recall).

Kappa is another useful metric for evaluation classification results. It measures the agreement between two raters (or the agreement between the predictions and the actual labels) while correcting for the agreement that happens by chance. It can be computed as:

$$\kappa = \frac{P_0 - P_1}{1 - P_1}, \quad (10)$$

where P_0 is the relative observed agreement between the predictive model and the ground truth, and P_1 is the probability that agreement is due to chance. Let us denote TP, FN, FP, TN as

a, b, c, d , respectively for simplicity, then P_0 and P_1 can be computed as below:

$$p_0 = \frac{a + d}{a + b + c + d}, \quad (11)$$

$$p_{11} = \frac{a + b}{a + b + c + d} \times \frac{a + c}{a + b + c + d}, \quad (12)$$

$$p_{12} = \frac{c + d}{a + b + c + d} \times \frac{b + d}{a + b + c + d}, \quad (13)$$

$$p_1 = p_{11} + p_{12}. \quad (14)$$

Kappa equals 1 for a complete agreement, which indicates perfect predictions, and 0 when it is a random predictor. A high Kappa suggests that the model’s performance in identifying erroneous versus correct samples is significantly better than random guessing.

PRC-AUC measures the area under the Precision-Recall Curve (PRC) that plots the precision (y-axis) against the recall (x-axis) for different thresholds. It quantifies the model’s overall performance across all threshold levels and is particularly useful for evaluating models on unequal datasets. The AUC for a PRC can range from 0 to 1, with a higher value indicating better model performance. An AUC of 0.5 suggests no discriminative power, equivalent to random guessing, while an AUC of 1 indicates perfect precision and recall.

7 Experiments

We designed a series of experiments to evaluate the validity of applying AL to data quality assessment and the effectiveness of AL in reducing labeling costs and dealing with severe data imbalance. The experiments can be summarized as follows:

- We examine classifiers’ robustness on datasets with different error rates and examine the impact of training samples on their performances.
- We assess the AL method’s ability to reduce labeling costs on data quality assessment tasks with different query strategies.
- We investigate AL’s efficacy in balancing the labeled set and enhancing classifiers’ performances under a strictly constrained number of training samples.

- We evaluate the effectiveness of constructing the initial set with outlier detection methods in initializing classifiers and reducing overall annotation costs.

7.1 Experimental Setup

7.1.1 Dataset

We build five datasets using records produced by five similar floats to reduce the influence of operational and environmental factors. Operational factors refer to those related to equipment manufacturing, such as platform maker, platform type, transmission systems and sensors. Environmental factors refer to the floats’ working conditions including deployed dates, locations, etc. We aimed to reduce the complexity of data analysis by controlling both types of factors that can impact sensor behaviors. The selected floats were equipped with the same sensors and deployed in the same month (March 2019) within the same area (Atlantic Ocean). The trajectories of these floats are depicted in Figure 4.

Fig. 4: Trajectories of the five floats. The floats drift over time but remain within the middle Atlantic area during the inspected time frame.

We consider six features (parameters), including *datetime*, *latitude*, *longitude*, *pressure*, *temperature* and *salinity*. The datasets have extensive quality labels for all the data samples provided by human analysts. When processing the quality flags, we treat features labeled as *good data* as error-free, denoted as 0, and others as erroneous, denoted as 1. Originally, the quality flags were assigned for each feature. To get a global quality label for observations, we treat one observation as 0 only if all the features have the label 0.

The statistics of the datasets are listed in Table 1. The dataset DS_{high} exhibits a substantial error rate of 33.72%, whereas the remaining four datasets, namely $DS_{low}1-4$, demonstrate exceedingly low error rates, all below 1%. Each dataset is randomly split into 60% training, 20% validation, and 20% test subsets while maintaining the same error rate for each subset. All the features undergo z-score normalization across the entire dataset from each float before feeding into the classifiers. Specifically, we transform each feature x_c^p by subtracting its mean μ^p and dividing by its standard deviation σ^p :

$$z_c^p = \frac{x_c^p - \mu^p}{\sigma^p} \quad (15)$$

This standardization centers each feature around a mean of 0 and scales it to have a standard deviation of 1. It is essential for models sensitive to feature scales, as it ensures that all features contribute equally to the model, improving convergence and performance.

We train separate models (sharing the same architecture) for each of the five floats using their respective data due to a significant “domain shift” observed between floats, which refers to the disparity in data distribution. This approach preserves the effectiveness of lightweight models without requiring complex adjustments for handling domain shifts.

7.1.2 Data Labeling

By design, experts are expected to provide annotations for specific observations. However, in our experiments, we bypass direct expert labeling as it would be too time-intensive for experimental purposes. Instead, we simulate expert involvement by using pre-labeled data. Initially, data labels are hidden, and the labels for selected observations are revealed only when requested by the model.

7.2 Classifier Performances

To benchmark various classifiers on handling uneven data given sufficient training samples, we first assess their performance across various datasets without using the AL method for training. This reflects the intrinsic resilience of classifiers toward class inequality. Then we examine how the quantity of training samples influences model

Table 1: Statistics of the datasets. Features are marked as *erroneous* unless labeled as “good data”. An observation is considered erroneous if there is at least one feature erroneous. *Error rate* refers to the ratio of observations denoted as erroneous in the dataset. The *Start date* is the same the launch date of the floats while the *End date* is simply the cutoff time for our data collection, not the retirement date of the floats. All selected floats were still active as of the data access time.

Dataset	Float code	Start date	End date	Error rate	Training samples	Test samples
DS_{high}	4903217	2019-03-21	2023-08-03	33.72%	179,539	59,847
DS_{low1}	4903218	2019-03-10	2023-08-02	0.84%	175,583	58,528
DS_{low2}	4903220	2019-03-07	2023-08-01	0.16%	181,009	60,337
DS_{low3}	4903052	2019-03-20	2023-07-27	0.69%	179,000	59,667
DS_{low4}	4903054	2019-03-23	2023-08-05	0.23%	177,455	59,152

performance by varying the size of the training set. Although the error ratios of various training sets are approximately the same, the actual number of erroneous samples will be distinct. This experiment suggests how the data imbalance and the shortage of labeled samples will jointly hinder the successful training of classifiers, which may not be so badly impacted in each individual situation. We compare the following types of models:

- Simple supervised classifiers, i.e., K-nearest Neighbor (KNN), Logistic Regression (LR) and RF;
- Gradient-boosted Decision Treess (GBDTs), i.e., XGBoost, CatBoost and LightGBM;
- Neural Networks (NNs) and variances of NN;
- Unsupervised anomaly detection models, i.e., LOF, iForest and Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN).

Their hyperparameters are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Models’ hyperparameter settings.

Model	Hyperparameters
KNN	Neighbors: 5; Leaf size: 30.
LR	Penalty: L2 distance; Random state: 42.
RF	Estimators: 20; Random state: 42.
XGBoost	Depth: 6.
CatBoost	Depth: 2, Iteration: 20.
LightGBM	Depth: 3 for DS_{low3-4} , 2 for others.
LOF	Neighbors: 20.
iForest	Estimators: 20; Random state: 42.
DBSCAN	Epsilon: 0.5; Minimum points: 10.

We exploit cost-sensitive learning to alleviate the class distortion challenge on NNs that utilizes binary cross-entropy loss functions. Specifically, we define custom class weights for the loss function that incorporates different costs associated with different classes. We denote NNs equipped with weighted losses as NN+CSX, where X is the weight for class 1 whereas the weight for class 0 remains 1 for all experiments. NN and NN+CSX adopt the same model architecture [Linear(6*32)+ReLU+Linear(32*2)], with two fully connected linear layers and one Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation layer in between. For the training processes, we utilize Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001. The epoch number is 10, and the batch size is 32.

7.2.1 Abundant Training Data Scenario

In this setting, classifiers are optimized using all samples from the training subset and then evaluated on the corresponding test subset. The outcome of this evaluation is presented in Table 3.

We find that distribution skewness poses great challenges to classifiers despite abundant training samples. Although classifiers can yield exceptional results on datasets with high error rates, their performance deteriorates on datasets with extremely low error rates. For instance, all 9 supervised classifiers achieve an F1-score of more than 0.99 on DS_{high} that has a 33.72% error rate, whereas the best F1-scores attained on DS_{low1} , DS_{low2} , DS_{low3} and DS_{low4} datasets with low error rates are 0.9316, 0.8901, 0.8045 and 0.7966, respectively.

Table 3: Classifier performances using all training data.

Dataset	Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Cohen’s kappa	PRC-AUC
<i>DS_{high}</i>	KNN	1.0000	0.9995	0.9998	0.9996	0.9997
	LR	1.0000	0.9995	0.9998	0.9996	0.9998
	RF	1.0000	0.9995	0.9998	0.9996	0.9998
	XGBoost	1.0000	0.9996	0.9998	0.9997	0.9999
	CatBoost	1.0000	0.9995	0.9998	0.9996	0.9999
	LightGBM	1.0000	0.9995	0.9998	0.9996	0.9998
	NN	1.0000	0.9995	0.9998	0.9996	0.9999
	NN+CS2	1.0000	0.9995	0.9998	0.9996	0.9999
	NN+CS5	1.0000	0.9995	0.9998	0.9996	0.9999
	LOF	0.3411	0.3411	0.3411	0.0059	–
	iForest	0.5385	0.5383	0.5384	0.3037	–
	DBSCAN	0.3372	1.0000	0.5043	0.0000	–
<i>DS_{low1}</i>	KNN	0.9977	0.8735	0.9314	0.9309	0.8947
	LR	1.0000	0.3816	0.5524	0.5504	0.5813
	RF	0.9470	0.8755	0.9099	0.9091	0.8980
	XGBoost	0.9954	0.8755	<u>0.9316</u>	<u>0.9311</u>	<u>0.9263</u>
	CatBoost	1.0000	0.7245	0.8402	0.8391	0.8787
	LightGBM	1.0	0.7959	0.8864	0.8855	0.8826
	NN	1.0000	0.7878	0.8813	0.8804	0.8763
	NN+CS2	1.0000	0.7918	0.8838	0.8830	0.8705
	NN+CS5	1.0000	0.7898	0.8826	0.8817	0.8592
	LOF	0.0367	0.0367	0.0367	0.0286	–
	iForest	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	–
	DBSCAN	1.0000	0.0163	0.0321	0.0319	–
<i>DS_{low2}</i>	KNN	0.9310	0.8351	0.8804	0.8803	0.8090
	LR	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.4257
	RF	0.9405	0.8144	0.8729	0.8727	0.8413
	XGBoost	0.9512	0.8041	0.8715	0.8713	<u>0.8581</u>
	CatBoost	0.9529	0.8351	<u>0.8901</u>	<u>0.8899</u>	0.8111
	LightGBM	0.9518	0.8144	0.8778	0.8776	0.7974
	NN	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.5853
	NN+CS2	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.6894
	NN+CS5	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.7879
	LOF	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	–
	iForest	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	–
	DBSCAN	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	–
<i>DS_{low3}</i>	KNN	0.9177	0.7073	0.7989	0.7977	0.7450
	LR	1.0000	0.0366	0.0706	0.0701	0.4130
	RF	0.8200	0.7000	0.7553	0.7537	0.7529
	XGBoost	0.9502	0.6976	<u>0.8045</u>	<u>0.8034</u>	<u>0.8303</u>
	CatBoost	0.9756	0.6829	0.8034	0.8023	0.7197

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Table 3 – Continued from previous page

Dataset	Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Cohen’s kappa	PRC-AUC
DS_{low3}	LightGBM	0.9757	0.6854	0.8052	0.8040	0.8008
	NN	0.9180	0.5463	0.6850	0.6834	0.7127
	NN+CS2	0.7712	0.6659	0.7147	0.7128	0.6749
	NN+CS5	0.8590	0.6390	0.7329	0.7313	0.7055
	LOF	0.0073	0.0073	0.0073	0.0004	–
	iForest	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	–
	DBSCAN	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	–
DS_{low4}	KNN	0.9010	0.6842	0.7778	0.7773	0.6731
	LR	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0655
	RF	0.8411	0.6767	0.7500	0.7495	0.7037
	XGBoost	0.9126	0.7068	<u>0.7966</u>	<u>0.7962</u>	<u>0.7222</u>
	CatBoost	0.9263	0.6617	0.7719	0.7715	0.6782
	LightGBM	0.9355	0.6541	0.7699	0.7695	0.7134
	NN	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.1662
	NN+CS2	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.1299
	NN+CS5	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.2266
	LOF	0.0149	0.0150	0.0150	0.0128	–
	iForest	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	–
DBSCAN	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	–	

Nevertheless, error rate isn’t the only factor impacting classifier performance. For instance, comparing to DS_{low3} and DS_{low4} , DS_{low2} exhibits the lowest error rate; however, classifiers achieve superior F1-scores on DS_{low2} . Additional reasons include inconsistencies in labeling or inadequacy of the model. Addressing labeling inconsistency necessitates further in-depth examination, and enhancing model competence requires the application of more advanced learning techniques. However, this specific issue is not the focus of this work; instead, in this work, we concentrate on diminishing the expenses associated with annotations. Thus, we consider the performance of classifiers optimized with full training data as the empirical goal for AL methods. Our objective is to attain this goal using as few labels as possible.

Compared with others, GBDTs including XGBoost and CatBoost are most effective on highly disproportionate data. XGBoost obtains the highest F1-score, Kappa and PRC-AUC on DS_{low1} , DS_{low3} and DS_{low4} while CatBoost the highest F1-score and Kappa on DS_{low2} . LightGBM exhibits robustness towards data

imbalance, though it achieves slightly lower performances.

KNN achieves performance levels close to the best-reported results based on F1-score, Kappa, and PRC-AUC. It performs comparably on DS_{low1} , DS_{low2} , and DS_{low3} , with a slight drop in performance on DS_{low4} . Similarly, RF remains effective with skewed datasets, generally producing lower F1-score and Kappa, but higher PRC-AUC compared to KNN across all four datasets: DS_{low1} , DS_{low2} , DS_{low3} , and DS_{low4} . These findings suggest that RF can offer better discrimination when its decision threshold is optimized. In contrast, the LR algorithm is highly sensitive to severe class distribution issues. It often shows high precision but low recall, or it completely fails. For instance, on DS_{low1} and DS_{low2} , LR achieves perfect precision (1.0), correctly identifying all predicted erroneous samples, but with very low recall, indicating many erroneous samples are missed.

NNs’s performances manifest high dependency on datasets. For instance, NN, NN+CS2, and NN+CS5 perform even better than CatBoost and LightGBM on DS_{low1} concerning F1-score and

Fig. 5: Performance of classifiers with different ratios of labeled data.

Kappa. They also achieve decent performance on DS_{low3} , where the weight increase for the minority class improves the F1-score and Kappa. However, they fail on DS_{low} and DS_{low4} . It implies that these datasets may conform to distinct hypotheses w.r.t. data distribution so that some datasets are easier to be classified by NNs than others.

When comparing unsupervised methods, including LOF, iForest, and DBSCAN, to supervised methods, including KNN, LR, RF, XGBoost, CatBoost, LightGBM, and NNs, the experimental results suggest that unsupervised models have completely failed on all datasets, regardless their error rates. For example, on DS_{low2} , LOF, iForest, and DBSCAN perform nearly like random guessing according to their Kappa scores.

In summary, XGBoost, CatBoost, LightGBM, and KNN among all investigated classifiers are most robust against severe class disparity when provided with plentiful training samples. Subsequently, we will employ these models as the learners for AL methods.

7.2.2 Impacts of Training Data Size

Considering that there are more than 100K training samples but only 6 features, classifiers might have been saturated by the training subset. To examine the necessary amount of labeled samples required for model training, we randomly select certain amounts of samples from the training subset and use them to train the classifiers. Following the experimental findings in Section 7.2.1, we utilize the XGBoost, CatBoost, LightGBM, and KNN for the experiments in this part.

We conduct experiments on all datasets and employ the F1-score to compare the performance of the classifiers. The results are presented in Figure 5. We find that most classifiers indeed require a smaller amount of training data to gain the same performance, and adding more training samples does not lead to the improvement of performance. For example, on all datasets, XGBoost, CatBoost, and KNN can achieve their best F1-scores using less number of training samples. One exception is LightGBM, the performance of which on DS_{low2} and DS_{low4} fluctuate greatly as the amount of training data changes.

Moreover, severe data disproportion can exacerbate the issue of data scarcity, implying that a highly uneven dataset necessitates more training samples. It can be illustrated by two observations. First, on datasets DS_{low1} , DS_{low2} , DS_{low3} , and DS_{low4} all classifiers' performances plunged as the ratio of labeled data decreases, especially between [0%, 10%] training data, whereas on DS_{high} they are not obviously affected and still yield a nearly perfect F1-score when the sampling ratio is as low as 0.1%. Second, while DS_{high} requires less than 1% of the training samples for classifier optimization, DS_{low1} requires more than 10% of the training samples, which shows that datasets with lower error rates tend to need more training samples for convergence.

These findings establish the practical basis for AL, which aims to refine model optimization by proactively selecting informative samples through well-designed query strategies. As a result, these models are expected to achieve comparable performances with even fewer labeled samples than randomly shrinking the training set.

7.3 AL for Reducing Labeling Cost

The primary motivation for applying AL is to reduce labeling costs, where AL methods can maximize model performance with minimal labeled samples. Although data samples in our experimental datasets have been fully annotated with quality flags, these flags will be concealed until one data point is selected by AL query strategies for labeling. Then we will reveal the corresponding quality flag to mimic human experts, who are responsible for providing ground truth labels. In real-world applications, QC operators will benefit from this workflow to manually label as few samples as possible.

This section evaluates the effectiveness of AL methods, primarily the query strategies, in improving model performance and reducing labeling costs. Specifically, we investigated two types of AL query strategies, i.e., Uncertainty-based Sampling (US) and Query-By-Committee (QBC) methods as described in Section 5.2.

7.3.1 Uncertainty-based Sampling

We examine the effectiveness of the Uncertainty-based Sampling (US) method by comparing it to Random Sampling (RS). The initial set is formed by randomly selected instances. Considering the error rates of the datasets, we set the initial set size to 100 for DS_{high} and 1000 for the DS_{low1} , DS_{low2} , DS_{low3} and DS_{low4} . Figure 6 shows the results for four classifiers on five datasets.

The results suggest that the US method is effective across all datasets with particularly strong performance on datasets of extremely low error rates. First, we observe that on DS_{high} XGBoost and CatBoost rapidly reach their best F1-score with less than 10 queried samples using US, while the RS method makes no difference in the models' performance throughout the AL cycles. LightGBM shows similar behavior though it needs more samples to optimize. An exception is KNN, where the RS method still increases its accuracy but takes much longer to achieve optimal performance compared to the US method. Compared with RS, US improve the F1-score for KNN, XGBoost, CatBoost and LightGBM on DS_{high} by 0.4%, 0.8%, 0.8%, and 1.8%, respectively. The subtle progress is due to the fair performance achieved by classifiers before the AL query process.

Second, US completely beats RS on four low-error datasets, i.e., DS_{low1-4} , regardless of classifiers. On DS_{low1} , compared with RS, the US approach increases the F1-score of KNN, XGBoost, CatBoost, and LightGBM by 465.5%, 46.8%, 47.1%, and 63.2%, respectively with merely 100 queried samples. And on DS_{low3} , the improvement of F1-score for KNN, XGBoost, CatBoost and LightGBM are 80.5%, 15.1%, 10.0%, and 17.8%, respectively.

On DS_{low2} and DS_{low4} , KNN and XGBoost report F1-score of 0 using RS but rapidly reach the highest F1-score with US. CatBoost and LightGBM see performance increase of 2.6% and 88.3% respectively on DS_{low2} , 3.2% and 44.1% respectively on DS_{low4} , when comparing US to RS.

Notably, the US approach can boost some classifiers' performance even better than using all the training samples. For example, on DS_{low4} , the F1-score of LightGBM has been increased by 112.7% using US compared with using all instances for training (see Table 3). One possible explanation is that fewer training samples can reduce the overfitting of LightGBM and improve its generalizability on unseen data.

7.3.2 QBC Sampling

With the second experiment, we evaluate the effectiveness of the Query-By-Committee (QBC) sampling method compared with the US approach. We use different combinations of classifiers to construct a committee and report the results on the four datasets with low error rates in Figure 7.

The experimental results indicate that ensembling different classifiers through the QBC strategy is less effective than using one single well-performed classifier. Generally, the combination of classifiers demonstrates an intermediate performance that positions between individual classifiers, and no improvement is observed compared with the best-performed one. Taking DS_{low3} as an example, the F1-score of the XGBoost+CatBoost committee falls between the F1-scores of XGBoost and CatBoost. The KNN+XGBoost+CatBoost committee outperforms KNN but is surpassed by the XGBoost+CatBoost committee due to the inadequate performance of KNN. Likewise, the ensemble of four classifiers compromises the performance of CatBoost.

Fig. 6: Comparisons of query strategies on different datasets. Legends denote the query strategies: “random” stands for random sampling, and “uncertainty” uncertainty-based sampling. (a)(b)(c)(d): DS_{high} ; (e)(f)(g)(h): DS_{low1} ; (i)(j)(k)(l): DS_{low2} ; (m)(m)(o)(p): DS_{low3} ; (q)(r)(s)(t): DS_{low4} . $K=1$ for all datasets.

Yet, this mechanism can still be leveraged to build a modest but generalizable model that can be applied across various datasets, rather than individual models customized for each dataset. Though the QBC methods incur more computational overheads compared to the US methods.

7.4 AL for Imbalanced Data Classification

Section 7.3 has demonstrated the effectiveness of AL query strategies in reducing annotation costs for data quality assessment. We also find that AL is effective in tackling distribution problems

Fig. 7: Comparison of various QBC methods. The x-axis is set to log scale for better visualization.

when there is a limited number of labeled samples. As demonstrated in Figure 6, on extremely unequal datasets, the F1-scores of classifiers KNN, XGBoost, CatBoost, and LightGBM that are trained on 1000 labeled samples, are still far lower than optimal. However, with 100 more labeled data instances selected by the US strategy, all

classifiers can achieve comparable results to these using all training data. As a comparison, 100 randomly selected samples usually cannot improve the performance of these classifiers.

7.4.1 Visualization of The Query Process

It is intriguing to gain insights into the underlying mechanism behind AL methods’ excellent results compared to the traditional learning process. We use DS_{low1} as an illustrative example, applying t-SNE analysis [38] for visualizing the query process.

As demonstrated in Figure 8, all classifiers, including KNN, XGBoost, CatBoost and LightGBM, that employ the US approach are inclined to select samples from areas occupied by erroneous data samples. By contrast, the RS method selects arbitrary samples across the entire population.

7.4.2 Implicit Data Balancing

In this part, we demonstrate that the labeled set has been balanced with selected samples by the AL query strategy, which largely contributes to the improved performance of the underlying classifiers. Table 4 reports the number of real erroneous instances chosen by different classifiers for labeling within 100 AL iterations.

We observe that the US method can select a non-trivial number of erroneous samples to form a more balanced labeled set. For instance, the US method assists classifiers in choosing maximum 57, 89, 82, and 64 erroneous samples from datasets DS_{low1} , DS_{low2} , DS_{low3} , and DS_{low4} respectively. On DS_{low1} , the US approach helps XGBoost, CatBoost, LightGBM, and KNN to spot 64, 57, 52, and 30 erroneous samples, respectively. Recall that the four datasets all have less than 1% erroneous data points, where random sampling will still result in severely uneven labeled data. Specifically, on all datasets, RS selects on average either 0.75 or 0 erroneous data samples. This may explain the effectiveness of the US method (see Figure 6), as erroneous samples are better pinpointed by the classifiers to enhance their ability to distinguish between normal and abnormal samples.

Nonetheless, the final performances of classifiers are not entirely dependent on the number of erroneous samples contained in the labeled set. For example, CatBoost has identified the most amount of erroneous samples on DS_{low1} and DS_{low4} , but it does not report the best F1-scores on these two datasets.

Table 4: Number of erroneous data points queried by classifiers in AL cycles. The F1-score and the number of erroneous samples for the random sampling method are the average values of all four classifiers. Initial set size: 1000. Query budget: 100; K:1.

Dataset	Query	Model	F1	Errors
DS_{low1}	RS	–	0.4904	0.75
		KNN	0.6933	30
	US	XGBoost	<u>0.9325</u>	64
		CatBoost	0.9314	<u>57</u>
		LightGBM	0.9314	52
DS_{low2}	RS	–	0.0101	0
		KNN	0.8901	82
	US	XGBoost	0.8901	52
		CatBoost	0.8901	<u>89</u>
		LightGBM	0.8901	75
DS_{low3}	RS	–	0.6408	0.75
		KNN	<u>0.8137</u>	<u>82</u>
	US	XGBoost	0.8086	44
		CatBoost	0.8125	67
		LightGBM	0.7915	49
DS_{low4}	RS	–	0.3200	0
		KNN	0.7719	50
	US	XGBoost	<u>0.7753</u>	38
		CatBoost	0.7699	64
		LightGBM	0.7699	<u>64</u>

Note that the US approach is inherently designed for selecting samples that classifiers are most uncertain about when predicting their quality labels. It is not specifically instructed to choose samples from the minority class. The fact that the method eventually chooses a large amount of minority samples is likely that classifiers are generally more uncertain about their predictions on these samples during the AL process, or in other words, the samples from the minority class are usually difficult to classify.

Hence, we can conclude that the US method empowers classifiers to locate erroneous data samples for labeling due to their difficulty to classify and thus forms a more balanced labeled set compared with the RS method.

7.5 Impact of Initial Set

Until this point, the influence of the initial set on model performance has not been explored, including the number of instances it contains and the way it is constructed. Thus, in this section, we

Fig. 8: The t-SNE visualization of samples selected by different classifiers via different query strategies. Dataset: $DS_{low}1$; Initial set size: 1000; Query budget:100; K: 1.

discuss the role of the initial set in the whole AL process.

7.5.1 Initial Set size

To examine the impact of the size of the initial set on AL effectiveness, we conduct experiments with different numbers of labeled samples for initializing the classifiers. We then observe and analyze their performances throughout the AL cycles. We choose XGBoost as the learning model since it has reported robust performances across four datasets, as summarized in Table 4. Considering the randomness, we conduct each experiment 5 times where a fixed set of random seeds is employed to select samples from the dataset. In our experiments, we set the initial set sizes to $\{100, 200, 300, 400\}$ and the random seeds set to $\{84, 65, 34, 25, 3\}$. We set the query budget to 300 for all experiments to track the long-term

performance changes. The mean values and the Standard Error of Mean (SEM) values of F1-scores are plotted in Figure 9.

First, we observe that on some datasets classifiers experience the cold-start problem due to the inadequate initial samples. For example, XGBoost completely fails the AL process on $DS_{low}4$ when provided with 100 and 200 initialization samples. Moreover, an initial set size can jeopardize the subsequent AL procedure where classifiers' performances get stuck in a suboptimal state, which can be evidenced by dataset $DS_{low}4$ with 300 and 400 initialization samples and dataset $DS_{low}2$ with 100, 200, 300, and 400 initialization samples.

Second, on average, the classifier performance during the AL process rises as the size of the initial set increases. This phenomenon can be clearly observed on $DS_{low}1$ and $DS_{low}3$, where the mean F1-score with an initial set of 400 labeled samples sees the steepest increases along the number

Fig. 9: The impact of initial set size. The lines represent the mean values, and the shadow area indicates the SEM range. Legend: sample amounts of the initial set. Classifier: XGBoost; Query budget:300; K: 1.

of queried samples. It also implies that the necessary number of samples for initializing classifiers varies largely among datasets, even though they have similar error rates. For instance, 400 labeled samples will be more or less sufficient for DS_{low1}

and DS_{low3} to initialize the XGBoost classifier, but will not be enough for DS_{low2} and DS_{low4} .

Finally, we also find that the presence of erroneous samples in the initial set plays a significant role in the success of the AL process on

some datasets. For example, when selecting samples from the dataset DS_{low4} using random seeds of 3 and 34, there is no erroneous data point included in all initial sets. As a result, XGBoost reports F1-scores of 0 for corresponding experiments. Compared to this, utilizing random seeds of 65 and 84, the initial set begins to include erroneous samples when built from 300 and 400 labeled samples, and meanwhile, XGBoost reports F1-score increases over AL querying steps. One exception is using a random seed of 25, where XGBoost still fails given 400 labeled samples with 1 erroneous sample.

Concluding from the above findings, using a pre-defined initial set size across datasets likely leads to a waste of annotation budget or failure of model training. Incorporating erroneous instances can potentially solve the cold-start problems and improve the effectiveness of the AL method.

7.5.2 Effectiveness of Using Outlier Detectors for Initial Set Construction

The conclusions drawn from Section 7.5.1 inspire us to introduce erroneous samples into the initial set to solve the cold-start problem and to reduce the initial set size. Although the experimental results suggest an unsatisfying classification capability of unsupervised outlier detection methods (see Section 7.2), their advantages in not needing any label information can still be leveraged to select erroneous observations, which is critical for the initial set construction.

We assume that some erroneous samples will appear as outliers and thus can be identified by outlier detectors. The outlier detectors being investigated are iForest [32], OCSVM [33], and LOF [34]. We conduct experiments with various classifiers on dataset DS_{low4} , which has reported serious cold-start issues under insufficient initialization samples. We use OCSVM with non-linear kernels (RBF). $N_I/2$ randomly selected samples are used to train OCSVM, together with the top- $N_I/2$ predicted anomalous samples to form the initial set. The number of estimators in iForest is set to 100. The number of neighbors in LOF is set to 10. The contamination value for iForest and LOF are defined as the dataset’s error rate. The numbers of erroneous samples identified by these outlier detection methods are listed in Table 5.

Table 5: The number of erroneous samples identified by outlier detection methods on DS_{low4} . N_I stands for the initial set size.

Method	# Outliers in N_I			
	$N_I=100$	$N_I=200$	$N_I=300$	$N_I=400$
iForest	0	0	0	0
OCSVM	0	0	0	0
LOF	4	6	14	21

Compared with using random selection to build the initial set, LOF can largely reduce the size of D_I to contain erroneous instances. LOF successfully recognizes 4, 6, 14, and 21 erroneous data points within the top 100, 200, 300, and 400 outliers they predict, respectively, while iForest and OCSVM fail to identify any erroneous data points. LOF is $4/100/0.0023 \approx 17$ times efficient in building the initial set containing erroneous samples in comparison with random selection.

Therefore, we employ LOF to construct the D_I , denoted as D_I^{LOF} , differing from the one formed by randomly selected instances, denoted as D_I^{RD} . To quantify the efficacy of the LOF-initialized AL method, we employ the reduced annotation cost as the evaluation metric. Let N_I be the minimum number of instances in the initial set that can start an effective AL procedure and N_L be the minimum number of instances in the labeled set that enable classifiers to reach their highest performances. Then we have the total annotation cost of $N_I + N_L$. The reduced cost $Cost_{\downarrow}$ is computed as:

$$Cost_{\downarrow} = 1 - \frac{N_I^{LOF} + N_L^{LOF}}{N_I^{RD} + N_L^{RD}}. \quad (16)$$

It ranges in $(-\infty, 1]$; the higher, the better. Table 6 summarizes the comparison results on dataset DS_{low4} .

The results suggest that our outlier detection-initialized AL method can successfully address the cold-start problem and significantly reduce the overall annotation cost to achieve comparable performances. Specifically, CatBoost and XGBoost manage to reduce the size of the initial set from 740 to 100, resulting in cost reductions of 76.9% and 56.5%, respectively, while maintaining the same F1-scores as randomly initialized counterparts. In contrast to CatBoost and XGBoost,

Table 6: The performance of initial sets built with random and LOF-based construction methods on dataset DS_{low}^4 . K:1.

Classifier	Random initialization			LOF initialization			$Cost_{\downarrow}$
	N_I	N_L	F1	N_I	N_L	F1	
KNN	740	60	0.7719	400	212	0.7719	23.5%
XGBoost	740	68	0.7753	100	251	0.7753	56.5%
CatBoost	740	9	0.7719	100	73	0.7719	76.9%
LightGBM	740	258	0.7699	400	261	0.7706	33.8%

KNN, and LightGBM require more instances for initialization (400 opposed to 100), possibly due to their low efficiency in learning disproportionate classes. Yet, the LOF-based initialization method manages to reduce their costs by 23.5% and 33.8%, respectively.

8 Conclusion, Discussion and Future Work

In this article, we proposed an AL-based QC-assistance framework to increase the efficiency of human experts on large-scale ocean observatory data. We identified two main challenges commonly encountered by ocean data quality assessment tasks, i.e., heavy manual workload and severe data imbalance. We leveraged AL’s ability to select the most informative samples and thus significantly reduced the amount of labeled data samples requiring human examination. To address the data distribution challenge, we first selected classifiers robust to distribution skewness, e.g., XGBoost and CatBoost, and then incorporated them with AL. The proposed method achieved increases in F1-score of KNN, XGBoost, CatBoost, and LightGBM by 465.5%, 46.8%, 47.1%, and 63.2%, respectively with merely 100 queried samples.

Towards the cold-start problem, we have to include erroneous observations within a small size of the initial set. We employed outlier detectors to sort out the most anomalous samples from the unlabeled set to build such an initial set. As suggested by the experimental results, the LOF-based initial set construction approach successfully identified 3 erroneous instances within top-100 ranked samples and accomplished a great decrease of annotation cost by 76.9% for CatBoost.

To our knowledge, this is the first study dedicated to applying AL to ocean data quality assessment, particularly focusing on highly imbalanced data. Our proposed framework provides general guidance for designing semi-automated QC workflows, where various query strategies, learning models, initial set construction methods, and AL iterative processes can be explored and exploited. The promising experimental results on five Argo floats data show the potential of this methodology. Extrapolating from this work, the application of AL in QC tasks is not restricted to the human-in-the-loop learning paradigm, where human experts must be present to provide labels. Even with all labels available beforehand, AL methods can still be leveraged to distill datasets either to address data problems, e.g., distribution disproportion and label noise, or to save computing and storage resources.

Nonetheless, there are some limitations associated with this work. First, classifier performances remain sub-optimal on highly uneven datasets, which calls for data-cleaning operations or more proficient learning models. Conflicts may exist in data distribution resulting from the inconsistency of data labeling over a long time period. The chosen models might not be capable of discovering effective patterns. Second, we exploit pool-based AL methods, which require access to the entire dataset and might be unsuitable for real-time applications. Stream-based AL that decides on the current instance for labeling could be more appropriate in such scenarios. Third, we have simplified the QC process to a binary classification problem, which does not differentiate between various error types or uncover the physical origins of these errors. Typically, Argo data undergoes rigorous, multi-step QC tests to identify errors due to drift, spikes, transient dirt, and more. The

delayed-mode QC testing relies heavily on experts' deep knowledge to identify, classify, and pinpoint different types of errors. To enhance support for QC experts, model development should integrate as much expert insight as possible. Finally, we use a small portion of Argo observatory data, training models for each float individually. This approach simplified the model training process, allowing us to utilize straightforward models like XGBoost instead of more complex deep learning methods. It also enables us to focus on evaluating the effectiveness of active learning in minimizing labeling costs in the context of severe data imbalance. Nonetheless, the scalability and robustness of the proposed method still need validation on larger datasets.

In the future, we plan to examine various error types and their origins to create tailored representations for each, enabling more precise human intervention. Following this, we aim to explore quality assessment methods at the parameter level, where each parameter receives its own quality flag, allowing for more detailed quality labeling. In terms of data representation, there is potential to develop foundational models specifically for Argo data, leveraging the vast historical datasets available. By pre-training on extensive ocean observatory data, such as the records collected by thousands of floats over several years, these advanced models would gain significant insights into ocean observations, making them suitable for quality control across diverse floats, regions, and seasonal variations.

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